

Development of Visualizations for Social Network Analysis of Chatroom Text

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ABSTRACT

In this paper a set of visualization tools and related ideas are introduced for extracting and analyzing social network features present within persistent, multi-speaker, multi-topic, quasi-synchronous computer-mediated communication systems enacted over the internet, i.e., internet chatrooms. Preliminary models of these tools are applied to a real-world chatroom dataset. Results suggest the utility of such tools for enhancing the usability of digital text communications and the understanding of social structures and dynamics within the virtual world. Potentially promising visualization methods and areas of future research are discussed.

KEYWORDS: Information Visualization; Text Mining; Social Network Analysis; Visual Interface Design; Human-Computer Interaction; Computer-mediated Communication.

1. INTRODUCTION

Chat is a unique form of computer-mediated communication (CMC) that involves the exchange of digital text messages between one or more users online. It is unique in that it is persistent (logs are often accessible over time), can be multi-speaker, is often multi-topic, and is quasi-synchronous (communicators are often, but not required, to be on-line for meaningful communications to occur). These features characterize most internet chatrooms. There has been increasing interest in visualizing aspects of chat to improve users' experience, since this type of digital communication is missing key aspects of normal face-to-face communications (interactional coherence, social cueing and turn-taking,

etc.) or have unique features altogether that might be useful -- or perhaps detrimental -- to users (persistence of logs, can be quasi-synchronous, etc.) [1-3].

There has been particular interest in extracting and/or visualizing social network and CMC data (comprehensive reviews of digital text visualizations can be found in [4,5]). The purposes of analyzing/visualizing this information are varied, and range from serving as statistical benchmarks, for increasing social consciousness and interaction, for improving educational interactions, and for improving usability, navigability, and understanding of conversations and topics under discussion [6-9]. Mutton [10] notes the importance of visualizing or otherwise graphically representing social networks since this allows viewers "to determine facts about nodes and relationships between nodes more rapidly than examining the raw mathematical model" or the raw text data.

The present work is meant to discuss our preliminary work towards extracting social network information from chat text data, and propose some methods of visualizing this information. Our approach to extracting social network information primarily includes:

- analyzing messaging response time patterns of and between members (temporal proximity)
- determining message similarities (based on keywords of message content)

The point of analyzing these two pieces of information is for constructing networks of who people are communicating with, and who is in a group or a given conversation/topic at any given time. Our method is unique in that most other methods appear to construct networks simply based on who is a member of a self-selected and clearly delineated conversation or group, or who is responding explicitly to whom (via signaling such

as “respond to” functionality present in emails, blogs, or newsgroups). Thus, determining social structures in chat rooms is less straightforward than in other seemingly similar CMC domains due to the lack of explicit signaling, because in other domains these relationships are usually made obvious or are otherwise explicit [11].

The idea of using a “temporal proximity” approach (with other similar interactional measures) to infer social networks in chat was proposed by Mutton [10], who then visualized them using edge-and-node diagrams using IRC data. Our analysis adds the analysis of message content to infer message similarity, with the goal of making more accurate inferences regarding who belongs in any given network, and their relationships to others. Additionally, we discuss and present some alternative visualizations of this data beyond the traditional edge-and-node network diagrams.

The methods discussed herein are applied to a subset of real-world chat dataset (i.e., communications logs). Our methods were designed primarily for passive outside observers of persistent chat systems but could easily find utility with users for active communications and collaborations.

2. CHAT DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

We present next our methods of analysis that were applied to portions of a free public chat dataset that contains over 14 million messages. This chatroom is primarily for fans of music (it’s called “MusicBrainz”) and has kept a persistent text record of all chats for the last seven years and, as of this writing, the chatroom continues to the present day [12]. For the data plotted in Figure 1, all messages were analyzed, while most of the visualizations were developed using snippets of the dataset, usually several thousand lines long. All screen names were changed to protect anonymity.

The chat data was gathered through either an application programming interface (API) or through a web crawler. We stored the full text of each message, which included such content as the username of the person who posted it, the date and time it was posted, and the text message itself sent by the user. We computed additional metrics including a count for how many times each word was used in a message, times between sequential message postings, and a unique ID for the message. System messages were generally disregarded or deleted (such as “Tom has logged on”).

2.1. Keyword Similarity

Messages were assigned a similarity score based on the number of shared keywords they contained in common with other messages. In this context we consider keywords as words that are most informative about the substance of the conversation. Currently, the keywords in our tool are generated using a variant of the *term frequency - inverse document frequency* (TF-IDF) [13]. They are the words that occur the most often in the entirety of the user generated chat messages after the elimination of *stop-words* (common words that are primarily uninformative, including conjunctions, pronouns, prepositions, etc. [13]. Although, we intend to improve the keywords identification method by using standard stop-word resources (e.g., a language dictionary for word sense disambiguation as well as synonyms clustering), the current method was reasonably effective for our initial development purposes.

2.2. Temporal Proximity

Virtually all forms of human communication show a similar temporal pattern: most people respond quickly most of the time, but very rarely, a few people take a very long time to make a reply in a conversation, whether in an email conversation, a spoken conversation, a pen-pal letter, or internet chat. This typically rapid response rate of course makes human communication very efficient; if someone doesn’t respond within a reasonable amount of time, they either didn’t get the message, or are signaling something else (like “leave me alone” or perhaps “I’m too busy to respond right now”).

In regards to the present topic of extracting social network data, large time gaps between sequential messaging provide a potential hint that a conversation has ended (and a new one started), while small time gaps between messages suggest the possibility that communicators are directly engaging with each other. Presented in Figure 1 is

Figure 1. Relative Frequencies of Message Response Times (in seconds) in an Internet Chat Sample. Note the y-axis is a logarithmic scale.

the relative frequency distribution of the response times between sequential messages of the MusicBrainz chat data, consisting of over 14 million messages. This data was used to calculate the probability that a given message was “in response” to the preceding message; thus helping us infer who was talking to whom.

2.2. Other Content Analysis – Direct Addressing

Our current system employs some of the popular methods of identifying direct messages in chatrooms, i.e., if a chat message referenced an individual communicator by screen name, called “direct addressing” by Mutton (2004). This type of observation is common in digital text communications, and is provided by speakers to enhance the clarity of who the message is intended for (and who it might not be intended for). When using this method, limitations arise when the chat message does not contain the screen name of any user (there simply is no direct addressing), or it contains a variation of the intended individual’s screen name (either intentionally or by typographical error).

5. PRELIMINARY RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the preliminary analysis of our tool suggests that it functions fairly well in constructing social networks in chatroom text, which can then be further analyzed and/or visualized possibly based on some of the ideas presented in the next section.

One of the major problems we encountered was that extremely short, terse messages that contained few non-stop-words, particularly if given after a substantial delay to the previous message, resulted in fragmenting of the conversational thread at some inappropriate points, thus splitting up some networks that should not have been fractured. An example of this problem was the short reply “Yes” or “No, I don’t” after a substantial delay to a particular question. This issue might be alleviated in future work by giving greater weightings to common “reply” words like “yes,” “no,” “maybe,” “ok”, etc. that follow a message with a question mark; or perhaps by giving users the ability in the software to “point” or otherwise easily indicate which message is being referred or replied to, although this last remedy has its own unique set of problems related to usability and compliance.

6. SOME PROPOSED VISUALIZATION METHODS

Next, we present some of our social network visualization ideas. One particularly promising technique was simply the plot of what we called the “conversation cycles” for a chosen individual (as shown in Figure 2 for “Mike”). One temporal “cycle” indicates the individuals who communicated with the chosen person, and how often, between the chosen person’s communications in time. One can quickly assess for Mike’s conversations who are the active communicators with him, whether the groups seemed to be dyads, triads, or larger, and how often they spoke before Mike communicated next. The cycles are arranged vertically in time. Vertical patterns tend to indicate continuing/on-going conversations with individuals (for instance, with Jane for cycles 1 to 7, then with Lindsey for cycles 7 to 17), while horizontal patterns indicate groupings (in cycle 17, Mike, Jane, Fred, Lindsey and Joe all seemed to be interacting). This visualization method may suffer from scaling issues, but we thought it a unique way to try to infer groupings, see temporal patterns, and see individual interactions all within a single visualization.

Another visualization idea we considered is similar to a covariance matrix (but using relative frequency of contacts instead of co-variances), as presented in Figure 3. As can be observed, individual communicators and their connectedness to others can be quickly viewed. One disadvantage of this method, again, is that for very large numbers of communicators, these graphics would get complicated very quickly. Additionally, this shows connectedness between individual communicators, but does not indicate who is a member of which group (or network), the way an edge-and-node diagram easily does. For instance, while Jane and Mike talked frequently, did their conversations also include Bob? In other words, is Bob part of Jane’s and Mike’s social network...it is not immediately clear using the visualization technique in Figure 3, but it is a question a user or a viewer could conceivably wish to know the answer to.

6. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

Future research might assess scaling for these proposed visualizations; in other words, at what point (i.e., how many communicators does it take) for these types of graphics to become perceptually or cognitively unwieldy? What other visualization methods might be more useful? Are nodes-and-edges sufficient? How do the tasks of the user shape the required visualizations?

Figure 2. An example Conversation Cycle graphic for Mike. We can see that Mike spoke in individual conversations with Jane, then Lindsey, then interacted more sporadically with others. Horizontal patterns suggest social network groupings (as in cycle 17).

In this work, we attempted to build upon the similar work of others, particularly that by Mutton [10], to develop tools and visualizations that might aid in social network analysis of chat data. Our focus here was on the persistent logs of chatrooms, as much of the work has focused on extracting social data for other purposes than network

analysis, such as for enhancing the educational or social experiences of users. But these ideas could conceivably be applied to other types of distributed electronic text communications to aid in analysis or enhancing usability, such as Twitter or texting logs, IM, web-logs or “blogs”, newsgroup comment logs, e-mail, etc.

In the future, it was suggested that sentiment analysis could also be implemented to try to determine the emotional content of entries (such as the display of positive, negative, or neutral mood by message posters). Using such methods might be akin to “emotional” threading as opposed to conversational threading, allowing users to avoid highly negative conversations or single negative messages within conversations, for instance, or for users more interested in the substantive informational content in a thread rather than the emotionally-charged content, whether positive or negative.

We also would like to attempt the correlation of information from chat messages with information from other digital sources in order to establish relationships or trends. For example, if a number of the musicians being talked about in the chatroom have become successful over the past seven years (and hence information in other media e.g. newspapers). Or, perhaps it would be useful to study the rate/flow of information between various communication systems (how does info flow through other similar or even dissimilar networks, and why?).

For our own future work, we would like to continue in the development of these visualization tools. At this point our ideas are still at a preliminary stage of development and require much further technical work. Also, usability testing, particularly formal experimental techniques are needed. We hope the discussion and preliminary results presented in this work can help guide our future work and (hopefully) others working on similar technical problems in information visualization, text-mining, social network analysis, and distributed collaborative communication systems and technologies.

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Jane	Mike	Bob	Eric	Mary	Shelly	Fred	Joe	Kate	Lindsey	Martha	Paul	George	
	100	27	32	0	23	28	23	23	24	0	0	21	Jane
100		30	27	32	24	48	24	51	51	25	23	22	Mike
27	30		26	0	0	21	0	0	0	0	21	0	Bob
32	27	26		0	21	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Eric
0	32	0	0		0	26	0	0	23	0	0	0	Mary
23	24	0	21	0		22	0	21	22	0	0	0	Shelly
28	48	21	0	26	22		30	34	53	0	25	0	Fred
23	24	0	0	0	0	30		0	26	0	0	0	Joe
23	51	0	0	0	21	34	0		44	23	21	0	Kate
24	51	0	0	23	22	53	26	44		0	23	0	Lindsey
0	25	0	0	0	0	0	0	23	0		0	0	Martha
0	23	21	0	0	0	25	0	21	23	0		0	Paul
21	22	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		George

Figure 3. An Example Contact Matrix. This displays who is talking to whom, and with what relative frequency.